

Nuclear stellar structures in barred galaxies of the TIMER survey

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Bars are frequent structures in disc galaxies, especially in the local Universe where approximately 2/3 of them host bars. Although this bar fraction is decreasing with increasing redshift, there is still a substantial fraction of bars evident at $z \sim 1$ while in some massive galaxies bars have even been detected as early as redshift 2 [1, 2]. Given that bars are robust structures that are difficult to destroy [3], they interact with their host galaxies over timescales of many Gyr. This makes bars one of the major drivers of secular evolution in disc galaxies and, in fact, these stellar structures influence their host galaxies in a variety of ways. For instance, bars are promoting the inflow of gas from the main galaxy disc to its centre. This gas inflow is halted in the central regions of disc galaxies at radii a few hundred parsecs from the galaxy centre. There the gas settles and facilitates the formation of sub-structures, in particular nuclear discs, nuclear rings, and inner bars [4, 5].

Our goal is to better understand the formation, evolutionary history, and physical properties of these bar-built central structures in disc galaxies. To this end, we use observations with unprecedented spatial resolution, obtained with the MUSE (Multi-Unit Spectroscopic Explorer; [6]) integral-field spectrograph for a sample of 21 Milky Way-like galaxies in the local Universe. The observations were performed as part of the TIMER Survey [7] and cover the central 1 arcmin² of the galaxies with a spatial sampling of 0.2 arcsec, resulting in a data-set of approximately 90 000 spectra per galaxy.

Based on this unique data set, the TIMER collaboration has investigated various aspects of the central components of galaxies, including the variation of stellar population properties along and perpendicular to the major axis of main bars [8], the stellar feedback from star formation in nuclear rings [9], differences in the kinematics of young and old stellar populations [10], and the physical nature of inner bars [11, 12, 13].

In the following we summarise the results of two recent TIMER studies constraining the formation and physical properties of nuclear discs and nuclear rings by deriving their stellar kinematics and mean stellar population properties [14, 15]. To this end, we employ the modular software framework of GIST** (Galaxy IFU Spectroscopy Tool; [16]) to facilitate the efficient analysis of the data and a rich visualisation of the results.

The Nature of Nuclear Stellar Structures

The analysis of the stellar kinematics of the TIMER sample clearly shows that nuclear discs are characterised by high rotational support, i.e. they exhibit high rotation velocities, low velocity dispersion, and show signs of near-circular orbits, as indicated by a strong anti-correlation of

velocity and the higher-order moment h_3 of the line-of-sight velocity distribution (see Figure 1). These results are consistent with the picture of bar-driven secular evolution in which a bar funnels gas to the galaxy centre where it settles and forms a new stellar component in a kinematically cold configuration. In addition, we find a clear correlation between the kinematic size of the nuclear discs (i.e. the radius at which v/σ peaks) and the length of the bar. As this correlation is stronger than the correlation between the size of the nuclear disc and main galaxy disc, it reinforces the strong physical connection between bars and nuclear discs.

Figure 1: Spatially resolved maps of the stellar velocity, velocity dispersion, and higher-order moments h_3 and h_4 of the galaxy NGC 4643. The nuclear disc is clearly discernible as a rapidly rotating central component with low stellar velocity dispersion.

Spatially resolved maps of the stellar population properties reveal that nuclear discs are significantly younger and more metal-enriched, as compared to their immediate surroundings (see Figure 2). This is expected in the bar-driven formation scenario, as the main disc and bar would, thus, form before the nuclear disc. In addition, the low $[\alpha/\text{Fe}]$ abundances of the nuclear discs indicate a slow but prolonged star-formation activity, again as expected in the picture of a bar-driven formation. This finding clearly contrasts with the formation of old and kinematically hot classical bulges in violent accretion events and their typically elevated $[\alpha/\text{Fe}]$ abundances.

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Figure 2: Spatially resolved maps of stellar ages, metallicities, and $[\alpha/\text{Fe}]$ abundances of the galaxy NGC 1433. The nuclear disc exhibits significantly lower stellar ages, high metallicities, and depleted $[\alpha/\text{Fe}]$ abundances, as compared to its immediate surroundings.

The Inside-out Formation of Nuclear Discs

While these young and kinematically cold nuclear discs are found in all galaxies of the TIMER sample, prominent nuclear rings are detected in only a few of them. The main difference between those galaxies hosting nuclear discs with and without nuclear rings is the availability of gas in the centre. Galaxies without nuclear rings exhibit barely any gas in their central regions. However, in galaxies with a significant amount of gas this gas is highly concentrated in a ring at the outer edges of the nuclear discs, i.e. in nuclear rings. In other words, nuclear rings can be understood as the gaseous outer edges of nuclear discs and seem to simply highlight the spatial region in which the bar-driven gas inflow is halted (see Figure 6 of [14] for a comparison of galaxies with and without nuclear rings).

Since the available gas in the galaxy centre is strongly concentrated in the nuclear rings, star formation also predominantly proceeds there. However, nuclear discs are found to be continuous stellar components that extend to the very centres of these galaxies. How is it possible that continuous stellar nuclear discs are formed if star-formation is in all cases limited to the gaseous nuclear rings at their outer edges? The explanation for this ques-

tions can be found in the co-evolution of nuclear rings and the bars that facilitate the gas inflow. More specifically, bars evolve considerably with time and tend to grow longer and stronger [17, 18]. In addition, we show that the radial extent of nuclear rings and bars is correlated, although it is still debated which precise physical process determines the radial size of nuclear rings.

In this picture, shortly after bar formation the bar is still comparably short resulting in the formation of a nuclear ring with small radius. As the bar evolves and grows longer and stronger, the nuclear rings should also grow in radius. As a result, a gaseous nuclear ring is located at each radius in the nuclear disc at any given point in time and, hence, a continuous stellar nuclear disc can be built from this series of star-forming nuclear rings with increasing radius. In fact, this inside-out formation scenario for nuclear discs is consistent with the negative gradients of stellar ages across nuclear discs (see e.g. Figure 4 in [14]) and was recently reproduced by numerical simulations [19].

References

- [1] Sheth, K., et al. 2008, ApJ, 675, 1141
- [2] Simmons, B. D., et al. 2014, MNRAS, 445, 3466
- [3] Athanassoula, E., et al. 2005, MNRAS, 363, 496
- [4] Combes, F. & Gerin, M. 1985, A&A, 150, 327
- [5] Piner, B. G., et al. 1995, ApJ, 449, 508
- [6] Bacon, R., et al. 2010, Proc. SPIE, 7735, 773508
- [7] Gadotti, D. A., et al. 2019, MNRAS, 482, 506
- [8] Neumann, J., et al. 2020, A&A, 637, A56
- [9] Leaman, R., et al. 2019, MNRAS, 488, 3904
- [10] Rosado-Belza, D., et al. 2020, A&A, 644, A116
- [11] de Lorenzo-Cáceres, A., et al. 2019, MNRAS, 484, 5296
- [12] Méndez-Abreu, J., et al. 2019, MNRAS, 482, L118
- [13] Bittner, A., et al. 2021, A&A, 646, A42
- [14] Bittner, A., et al. 2020, A&A, 643, A65
- [15] Gadotti, D. A., et al. 2020, A&A, 643, A14
- [16] Bittner, A., et al. 2019, A&A, 628, A117
- [17] Athanassoula, E. 2003, MNRAS, 341, 1179
- [18] Martínez-Valpuesta, I., et al. 2006, ApJ, 637, 214
- [19] Seo, W.-Y., et al. 2019, ApJ, 872, 5

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